

A TOP-LEVEL CMAKELISTS.TXT TEMPLATE

The template content for the top-level *CMakeLists.txt* for Cadmium projects is shown below. The purpose of this file is to initialize the project with the *CMake* build system and download the simulator as a dependency.

```
cmake_minimum_required(VERSION 3.20 FATAL_ERROR)

set(CMAKE_CXX_STANDARD 17)
set(CMAKE_CXX_STANDARD_REQUIRED True)

project(my_cadmium_proj)

#####
### Dependency Setup ###
#####
include(deps/cadmium2.cmake)           # Downloads cadmium and sets
up variables

#####
### Global Variables ###
#####
set(includes_list
    "${CADMIUM2_INCLUDE_DIR}"
    "${CMAKE_CURRENT_SOURCE_DIR}/deps"
    ${CMAKE_CURRENT_SOURCE_DIR}/include
    CACHE STRING "Test program Includes List"
)

#####
### Subdirectories ###
#####

add_subdirectory(test)
add_subdirectory(src)
```

B CADMIUM2.CMAKE TEMPLATE

The template code for downloading the Cadmium simulator as a dependency is shown below. This code is in the *cadmium2.cmake* file within the project tree template for *Cadmium2*.

```
include(FetchContent)

FetchContent_Declare(
```

```

cadmium2
GIT_REPOSITORY https://github.com/CurtisWinstanley/async_inputs_cadmium_v2.git
GIT_TAG dev-rt
GIT_PROGRESS TRUE
GIT_SUBMODULES "" # Do not initialize submodules
)

FetchContent_GetProperties(cadmium2)
if(NOT cadmium2_POPULATED)
  FetchContent_Populate(cadmium2)
endif()

set(CADMIUM2_INCLUDE_DIR ${FETCHCONTENT_BASE_DIR}/cadmium2-src/include CACHE
STRING "Cadmium2 Include File Location")

```

C CONFIGURED COMMANDS FOR CADMIUM2 IN PROMETHEUS

The tables for all commands required by the configuration of *Cadmium2* are shown below

Project Initialization Commands		
Windows	Apple	Unix
cd {PROJ_DIR}/build	cd {PROJ_DIR}/build	cd {PROJ_DIR}/build
cmake ..	cmake ..	cmake ..

Build Commands For Testing Models		
Windows	Apple	Unix
cd build	cd build	cd build
cmake --build . -t td_{MODEL_NAME}	cmake --build . -t td_{MODEL_NAME}	cmake --build . -t td_{MODEL_NAME}

Build Commands For Source Models		
Windows	Apple	Unix
cd build	cd build	cd build
cmake --build . -t {MODEL_NAME}	cmake --build . -t {MODEL_NAME}	cmake --build . -t {MODEL_NAME}

Run Commands For Testing Models		
Windows	Apple	Unix
{PROJ_DIR}/build/test/Debug/td_{MODEL_NAME}.exe	{PROJ_DIR}/build/test/td_{MODEL_NAME}.exe	{PROJ_DIR}/build/test/td_{MODEL_NAME}.exe

Run Commands For Source Models		
Windows	Apple	Unix
{PROJ_DIR}/build/src/Debug/{MODEL_NAME}.exe	{PROJ_DIR}/build/test/{MODEL_NAME}.exe	{PROJ_DIR}/build/test/{MODEL_NAME}.exe

D PROMETHEUS MANUAL: GENERATE TESTS FUNCTION

6.4.3 Function: `generate_tests`

For generating the code for your tests, we have provided the following function template with the following signature below.

```
def generate_tests(_input_port_data: dict,
                  _output_port_data: dict,
                  _constructor_data: dict,
                  _model_name: str,
                  _location_of_model: str,
                  _test_data: dict) -> dict:
```

In the following subsections, we will go over each field and its following contents/source.

6.4.3.1 Field Name: `_input_port_data`

The `_input_port_data` field of `generate_tests` contains the input port names and types for the model under test. This comes in the form of a dictionary of key-value pairs where the keys are the port names, and the values are the port types. The source of this data is from element 3 from figure 8. An example of what the data looks like is shown below.

```
{'my_input_port_1': 'int', 'my_input_port_2': 'float'}
```

In the example above, the model we are testing has two input ports: `my_input_port_1` of type `int` and `my_input_port_2` of type `float`.

6.4.3.2 Field Name: `_output_port_data`

The `_output_port_data` field of `generate_tests` contains the output port names and types for the model under test. This comes in the form of a dictionary of key-value pairs where the keys are the port names, and the values are the port types. The source of this data is from element 4 from figure 8. An example of what the data looks like is shown below.

```
{'my_output_port_1': 'std::string'}
```

In the example above, the model we are testing has one output port: `my_output_port_1` of type `std::string`.

6.4.3.3 Field Name: `_constructor_data`

The `_constructor_data` field of `generate_tests` contains the constructor argument names and types for the model under test. This comes in the form of a dictionary of key-value pairs where the keys are the argument names, and the values are the argument types. The source of this data is from element 5 from figure 8. An example of what the data looks like is shown below.

```
{'con_arg_1': 'int'}
```

In the example above, the model we are testing has one constructor argument: `con_arg_1` of type `int`.

6.4.3.4 Field Name: `_model_name`

The `model_name` field of `generate_tests` contains the model's name of the model under test. This comes in a simple string format. The source of this data is from element 1 from figure 8.

6.4.3.5 Field Name: `_location_of_model`

The `location_of_model` field of `generate_tests` contains the directory path string to where the model code is located. This path is partially the path defined by the users' path specification of the *Atomic Model Code Dir* in Section 6.2 with the appended model name at the end. An example of what the data will look like is shown below.

```
"C:/my_proj/atomic_models/MyModel"
```

In the above example, we can see that the specified code directory for this model is `C:/my_proj/atomic_models`. Additionally, we can see that the model we are testing is named `MyModel` and because of that its name is appended to the end of the path to make it `C:/my_proj/atomic_models/MyModel`.

6.4.3.6 Field Name: `_test_data`

The `test_data` field of `generate_tests` contains the test data that user populated in the Model Testing Interface shown in figure 7 for every test case. This comes in the form of a dictionary of key-value pairs where the keys are test case names and the values are dictionaries that contain the inputs to generate, outputs to expect, expected state transitions, and set constructor arguments for the model under test. The source of this data comes from all graphical elements in figure 7. An example of what the data looks like is shown below.

```
{'my_first_test_case': {'set_constructor_args':  
  [{'con_arg_1': ['4', 'int']}], 'State_Transitions':  
  ['STATE', 'STATE_2', 'STATE_3'], 'Inputs_Table':  
  {'my_input_port_1': {'data': [('1', '1')], 'port_type':  
    'int'}, 'my_input_port_2': {'data': [('5', '1.5')],  
    'port_type': 'float'}}, 'Outputs_Table':  
  {'my_output_port_1': {'data': [('10', '"output!"]'),  
    'port_type': 'std::string'}}}}
```

In the example above, we have a test case called `my_first_test_case`. This test case has set the constructor argument `con_arg_1` of the model to 4. It expects state transitions to occur in the order of `STATE`, `STATE_2`, and `STATE_3`. Inputs are generated at 1 second on input port `my_input_port_1` with value 1 and an input is generated at 5 seconds on input port `my_input_port_2` with value 1.5. An output from `my_output_port_1` is expected at 10 seconds with the value "Output!"